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SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL SURVEY OF ARACHNIDA

SANSA Newsletter 40

SANSA NEWSLETTER

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After 25 years, the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) is still going strong. A great deal of time and effort has been invested in generating an archive of data and output over the 25-year history of SANSA.

The South African professional (employed) arachnologists have already published >500 papers on South African spiders. This is an excellent resource on spiders of South Africa, as well as several documents such as the identification guides that are distributed over the internet. Many of these are enormously useful reference materials.

The scattered nature of this information makes it very difficult to manage and distribute and was developed before the advent of widely accessible online data repositories. To ensure the greatest possible usefulness and longevity of this information, the SANSA team made the decision to migrate the SANSA data to Zenodo.

What is Zenodo?

Zenodo is a general-purpose repository that allows researchers to deposit research related digital artefacts. Zenodo is offered and hosted by CERN, a memory institution for High Energy Physics and renowned for its pioneering work in Open Access. More information can be found at <https://about.zenodo.org/>. SANSA has registered and set up a community within Zenodo to archive data and output over the 25-year history of SANSA.

Anyone can access the SANSA community on Zenodo following this link <https://zenodo.org/communities/sansa/> and search for content within this community – some articles in peer-reviewed journals might have access restrictions, but the vast majority, such as the Spider Identification Guides, SANSA newsletters and SANSA articles will be freely downloadable. Migration of SANSA data will take place in February and March 2022.

You are also free to upload relevant content related to SANSA. You'd have to register with Zenodo to enable this functionality and these submissions will be curated by Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (DippenaarA@gmail.com).

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EDITORIAL COMMITTEE

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman
dippenaaransie@gmail.com

Rudi Steenkamp
rudolphsteinkampf@gmail.com

Nico Dippenaar
nicod@pixie.co.za

Distribution
Ruan Booysen
booyesenr@ufs.ac.za

Stefan Foord
stefan@foord.co

PETER WEBB – WE LOST A GREAT SANSA TEAM MEMBER

Peter receiving a Certificate of Merit from Stefan Foord at the 13th AFRAS Colloquium in recognition of his contribution to the African arachnological community. Photo credit Norman Larsen

We received the sad news that Peter Webb passed away at the beginning of January 2022 from pancreatic cancer. Peter was one of the first persons to contact me to offer to participate in the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA). Peter was not only an excellent field worker but he was also extremely handy with a camera.

Peter was a true naturalist with knowledge of many living creatures and plants. He and his wife, Laurie, loved to travel and weekends were spent sampling and photographing arachnids and insects. What made his contribution especially valuable is that specimens were photographed and the voucher specimens were collected.

He also frequently accompanied the SANSA teams to undertake surveys in nature reserves such as Aardvark, Ezemvelo Lekgalameetse, Roodeplaat, Rooipoort, Tswalu and Tswaing Crater. He also participated in a Bioblitz with the Lepidoptera people at Zandspruit, Lephahlale. His pet project was the six-year survey of a native grassland near Irene. Peter sampled and photographed 270 species from this small area. He was involved in several projects in and around Pretoria and we hope to publish the results in future newsletters.

Peter sampled and photographed arachnids from >90 localities throughout South Africa. He did not only take single photographs of a species but a series showing the spider from all angles. All the photographs were shared with SANSA. I have identified and sorted all of his photographs into families and according to the locality. To get some idea of the number of photographs Peter Webb has taken: Salticidae (15 020 images) and Thomisidae (9 260 images) and in total 719 GB photographs of 52 families. He was also very good at observing their behaviour and this is reflected in several articles published.

Peter is co-author of several scientific papers. He also contributed to several congresses and colloquiums. He was a good speaker and gave numerous talks to the public. In 2020 at the 13th African Arachnological Colloquium at Klein Kariba, he received a Certificate of Merit in recognition of his contribution to the African arachnological community. A Thomisidae species was named after Peter (*Heriaeus peterwebbi*) in recognition of his contribution to spider research.

We would like to extend our deepest condolences to his family; we know Peter will be remembered by all of the arachnologists.

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman

Peter at Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Photo credit Laurie Webb

Peter, Robin and Michael Stiller at Rooipoort.

Bioblitz at Zandspruit.

Peter at the 13th AFRAS Colloquium

Peter Webb and his wife Laurie sampling

SANSA PUBLIC TEAM MEMBERS

Over the years, several people contacted us to ask if they can participate in SANSA. We provided them with a code, bottles and alcohol for collecting. They have made an enormous contribution as many of them not only collected specimens but also photographed the live specimens. Many of them made some excellent observations, as can be seen the articles already published in the SANSA News. Numerous new species have also been collected and several species were named after these photographers. All the people listed here have collected >200 specimens for the SANSA database.

PHOTOGRAPHERS

We are also very grateful to all the photographers who are prepared to share their photographs with SANSA. For the Red Listing document we would like to have an image of every species in the country, but we are still far from this goal as we presently have identified images of only about 37% of our fauna.

For several families (e.g. Anapidae, Telemidae, Symphytonathidae) there are no photographs of live specimens. The same goes for a large number of genera and species of the burrow dwellers.

Unfortunately, for correct identification, we need the specimen to identify it under a microscope and the specimens then must be deposited in collections as voucher specimens.

Province	Photos	Collect	Information
GAUTENG			
Koos Geldenhuys	X	X	
Les Oates	X	X	
Renata Kruyswijk	X	X	X*
Vida van der Walt	X	X	X
Peter Webb	X	X	X*
EASTERN CAPE			
Marie de Jager	X	X	X*
Linda Wiese	X	X	X*
FREE STATE			
Allen Jones	X	X	X*
NORTHERN CAPE			
Reginald Christiaan	X	X	X*
WESTERN CAPE			
Victor Hamilton-Atwell	X	X	X*
Helen Lubbe		X	
Elton le Roux	X	X	X*
Zani van der Walt		X	X*
Walter Jubber	X	X	
* published information			

NEW TAXONOMIC CHANGES

In a new paper by Azevedo *et al.* (2022), several taxonomic changes were proposed and the following changes affect the fauna of South Africa:

- **AMMOXENIDAE** now regarded as a junior synonym of **GNAPHOSIDAE**.
- The family rank for **PRODIDOMIDAE** is restored with two subfamilies recognized in South Africa: **PRODIDOMINAE** and **THEUMINAE**.

AZEVEDO, G.H.F, BOUGIE, T., CARBONI, M., HEDIN, M. & RAMÍREZ, M.J. 2022. Combining genomic, phenotypic and sanger sequencing data to elucidate the phylogeny of the two-clawed spiders (Dionycha). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 166(107327): 1-14.

Ammoxenus amphalodes (Gnaphosidae) Peter Webb

Eleleis limpopo (Prodidomidae) Peter Webb

Salticids possible mimic of scale insects

Oviballus vidae Azarkina & Haddad, 2020. Photo credit: Vida v.d. Walt.

Rhene cooperi Lessert, 1925. Photo credit: Vida v.d. Walt.

Recently, two new salticids, *Rhene legitima* Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018 and *Oviballus vidae* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020, were described from South Africa. It was speculated that they mimic either scale insects (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) or lacewing larvae (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae). The morphological similarities between the mimic and its potential models is made possible through the presence of white setae covering the spider's body, together with a series of tufts of very long erect white setae on the carapace, abdomen and legs.

In a new paper by Haddad (2021), another species with white setae, *Rhene cooperi* Lessert, 1925, was redescribed.

REFERENCE

HADDAD, C.R. 2021. Rediscovery and redescription of *Rhene cooperi* Lessert, 1925 (Araneae: Salticidae), another possible mimic of scale insects. *Arthropoda Selecta* 30(4): 546-550. doi: 10.15298/arthscl.30.4.10

NEW SPIDER GENUS *BIJOARANEUS* REPORTED FROM SOUTH AFRICA

The spider *Araneus legonensis* that was described by Grasshoff and Edmunds (1979) from Ghana has distinct abdominal patterns and the species was first reported from South Africa by Dippenaar-Schoeman (2007). Heron (2017) reported on their interesting leaf-stitching behaviour.

In a recent paper, the species was placed in a new genus, *Bijoaraneus* Tanikawa, Yamasaki and Petcharad, 2021. The generic name is coined from the Japanese word "Bijo" (meaning "beautiful lady") and *Araneus*.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2007. Some more interesting photographs received. *SANSA Newsletter* 4: 3.

GRASSHOFF, M. & EDMUNDS, J. 1979. *Araneus legonensis* n. sp. (Araneidae: Araneae) from Ghana, West Africa, and its free sector web. *Bulletin of the British Arachnological Society* 4: 303-309.

HERON, H.D.C. 2017. *Araneus legonensis* Grasshoff & Edmunds, 1979 (Araneidae): New locality record and observations on ethology. *SANSA*

Bijoaraneus legonensis. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

TANIKAWA, A., YAMASAKI, T. & PETCHARAD, B. 2021. Two new genera of Araneidae (Arachnida: Araneae). *Acta Arachnologica* 70(2): 87-101.

Season determines the efficiency of a rapid sampling protocol for non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) in Afrotropical grassland biotopes

REFERENCE: BOOYSEN, R. & HADDAD, C.R. 2021. Season determines the efficiency of a rapid sampling protocol for non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) in Afrotropical grassland biotopes. *Austral Entomology* 60(4): 19-21 <https://doi.org/10.1111/aen.12573>.

Abstract

Since the initiation of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), there has been a considerable amount of work done regarding arachnid diversity in South Africa. This project investigated the non-acarine arachnid diversity in the western KwaZulu-Natal grasslands, specifically in semi-pristine and agricultural areas close to Newcastle. The biotopes of interest were situated at Ncandu Falls, Moorfield Mountain Farm and a *Eucalyptus* plantation at Normandien Farms. Here we tested how the SANSa rapid sampling protocol performed in collecting arachnids in two contrasting seasons, winter (June and July 2015) and summer (December 2015 and January 2016).

A total of 4 623 non-acarine arachnids were collected that were represented by 185 species in five orders. Winter showed the highest abundance of individuals collected (including juveniles), but summer had the highest adult species abundance and richness ($n=425$ and $n=139$ species respectively). On the other hand, winter yielded a low number of adults and species richness ($n=349$ and $n=89$ species respectively). Our results also showed that hand collecting during the day was the most efficient in sampling arachnid diversity and abundance. This method also sampled more unique species than the other methods. In contrast, the Berlese-Tullgren funnels delivered the least adequate results overall. Several other methods showed sample completion values below 50% on their own, but combined, their sample completion was above 50%, which is a good representation of the fauna sampled in the area.

This means that using various methods in unison throughout several biotopes is a much better approach to adequately sampling the diversity of arachnids in the area.

First author busy planting pitfall traps on the mountain slope at Moorfield Farm. Photo credit; Alex Wiersch

Camillina cordifera female.

Hahnia tabulicola female.

Thyene thynioides female.

Thyene thynioides male.

Metabiantes incertor male. Photo credits: Ruan Booysen.

Alien and invasive *Badumna longinqua*

Exotic species are organisms that occur outside their natural distribution ranges. These occurrences are driven by globalisation. A cursory glance at the World Spider Catalog will make it evident that there are several introduced species and South Africa is no exception.

A recent paper by Charles Haddad and Stefan Foord in the *Journal of Arachnology* (Haddad & Foord, 2021) documents the distribution of one such a species, the grey house spider, *Badumna longinqua*, introduced from Australia. This species is currently largely restricted to the southern coastal areas of the Cape, more specifically areas with year-round warm and humid conditions that vary little between seasons, such as Knysna and Tsitsikamma. However, they also occur in outlying areas as far north as plant nurseries in Bloemfontein, which is evidence of the impact that human transport can have on animal dispersal.

One important aspect of invasions is the pathways by which organisms colonise new areas. Grey house spiders might be transported on plants and plant material sold at these nurseries, while these places provide the humid and hot conditions they prefer. It seems plants are a common pathway for spider invasions.

Our own cheiracanthiid sac spiders have become invasive in Europe when they were transported there in fruit (grapes, peaches, etc.) containers. There are of course other pathways, chief among which is the pet trade in tarantulas. Oddly enough, people trading in exotic spiders and people abandoning their pet spiders could facilitate accidental introductions of these species. Cavin Shivambu and co-authors recently identified tarantula species in the pet trade and which of these could potentially become invasive (Shivambu *et al.*, 2020).

To control and mitigate against the impacts of aliens, the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has developed a unified approach to classifying aliens according to their environmental impact classification of alien taxa (EICAT) and socio-economic impact classification of alien taxa (SEICAT). Effective control of these alien species requires an understanding of not only the pathways of introduction, spread and the sites they could potentially invade, but also the organisms themselves.

In collaboration with Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman, we have identified 88 species that are potentially introduced to South Africa. The pathways of introduction and the impacts of these species would be of particular interest going forward but also the traits that make them successful at invading areas.

REFERENCES

HADDAD, C.H. & FOORD, S.H. 2021. Future climate may limit the spread of the Australian house spider *Badumna longinqua* (Araneae: Desidae) in South Africa. *Journal of Arachnology* 49(3): 332-339. <https://doi.org/10.1636/JoA-S-20-069>

SHIVAMBU, C.T., SHIVAMBU, N., LYLE, R., JACOBS-VENTER, R., KUMSCHICK, S., FOORD, S.H. & ROBERTSON, M.P. 2020. Tarantulas (Araneae: Theraphosidae) in the pet trade in South Africa. *African Zoology* 55: 323-336. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15627020.2020.1823879>

Badumna longinqua female. Photo credit: Linda Wiese.

Epigyne and palp after Haddad & Foord (2021).

Web made in a fence post, Kamma Park, Port Elizabeth. Photo credit: Charles Haddad.

A CASE FOR SPIDER (ARANEAE) BYCATCHES IN ECOLOGICAL STUDIES

REFERENCE: HADDAD, C.R. 2021. Undergraduate entomology field excursions are a valuable source of biodiversity data: A case for spider (Araneae) bycatches in ecological studies. *Biodiversity and Conservation* (2021)30: 4199-4222. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-021-02301-9>

The arachnid fauna of the semi-arid western parts of the Free State province remains poorly known, despite some sampling having been conducted in the southwestern parts of the province during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). Since 2015, the University of the Free State (UFS) has conducted arachnid collecting trips at the farm Bankfontein, on the western side of the Vanderkloof Dam, part of the Orange River system. This was in response to the development of a research camp on the farm by the owners, Joop and Val Fourie, for use by students, school groups and the public.

In 2016, the Department of Zoology and Entomology at the UFS started holding the annual third-year Entomology students' field excursion at Bankfontein, as it forms part of the transition zone between the Grassland and Nama Karoo biomes, a different environment to the moister grasslands of the central Free State that the students are familiar with. Excursions were held in 2015, 2016 and 2018-2020, with the last excursion being cancelled a week prior to its commencement, ahead of the first national COVID-19 lockdown.

Sampling in 2020 was therefore conducted by Charles Haddad and two PhD students, Ruan Booysen and Hannelene Badenhorst. Each year, the students were divided into groups of two or three students, depending on the number of students registered for the module, which determined the number of participating groups.

Sampling was carried out by each group using a standardised protocol, with 10 beat samples (50 beats each), 10 pitfall samples (96 hours each) and 10 leaf litter samples being taken in each of three biotopes: riparian woodland, hillside grassland and Nama Karoo veld. Students had to sort the samples in the field laboratory, identify all of the insects, and process the data to determine the faunal composition, vertical stratification in habitats and difference between habitats in arthropod diversity.

All of the arachnids were sorted, identified and tallied by Charles in the field, so that these data could be made available to the students. Over the five years of sampling, the morphospecies collected by students were used to build a comprehensive database of the sampled species, which was complemented by additional arachnid sampling by Charles, his postgraduate students, museum staff (Jan Andries Neethling) and visiting international researchers.

Considering all of the arachnids collected to date, 242 species of spiders have been sampled from Bankfontein, with several species of pseudoscorpions, four species of scorpions, one harvestman species, and several species of Solifugae also collected. The most species-rich families were Gnaphosidae (36 spp.), Salticidae (35 spp.), Thomisidae (21 spp.) and Theridiidae (18 spp.). These data were used to compare the success of each of the student groups, and the five years of excursion sampling, in determining the spider diversity of Bankfontein.

Over the five years, students sampled a total of 158 spider species, representing 65.3% of the local species richness of Bankfontein. The number of spider species sampled by each student group (90 samples in total) varied between 37 and 66, while in 2020, when the experienced arachnologists conducted sampling simulating two student groups, 95 and 99 species were collected from each set of 90 samples. When each year group was considered, species richness collected ranged between 57 and 94 species, with 119 species collected by the arachnologists in 2020.

This study demonstrated that although individual student groups and year groups collected a variable number of spider species, less than half of the local species richness, that when these data are accumulated and combined over a number of years that such excursions can sample a meaningful proportion of the local species richness of an area, in this case, almost two-thirds of the species. The other species not sampled by students were predominantly microhabitat specialists (e.g. living associated with rocks or grass tussocks, which were not sampled by students) or had limited phenologies, so they were not active in early autumn when the excursions were held, but were active at other times in the year when arachnologists also collected. Student excursions therefore represent a valuable source of biodiversity data, not only for spiders, but potentially for any group of organisms.

The farm Bankfontein, on the western side of the Vanderkloof Dam, part of the Orange River system. Photo credits: Charles Haddad

FIELD OBSERVATIONS

MORE ON A *DIPHYA* SPECIES

We received these interesting images from Wessel Pretorius of Malmesbury taken at Babylonstoren Klapmuts (33 49' 21.00" S 18 55' 48.00" E) in the Western Cape. He observed a small orb-web in dead wood and on closer inspection he was able to photograph the spider. The spider was identified as *Diphya simoni* Kauri, 1950.

According to Marusik (2017), there are no literature data about the natural history of *Diphya* species. Primary data of the *Diphya* species he studied in South Africa indicated that they are usually found on the ground among grass. He speculates that they possibly do not build webs but catch their prey with help of a "basket" formed by the spiny first pair of legs. Here is now the first record of *D. simoni* making a small orb-web.

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MARUSIK, Y.M. 2017. A review of *Diphya* (Aranei: Tetragnathidae) from South Africa. *Arthropoda Selecta* 262: 133-138.

OMELKO, M.M., MARUSIK, Y.M. & LYLE, R. 2020. A survey of *Diphya* Nicolet, 1849 (Araneae: Tetragnathidae) from South Africa. *Zootaxa* 4899(1): 259-279.

Diphya simoni as photographed at Klapmuts by Wessel Pretorius.

INTERESTING FEEDING BEHAVIOUR OF A THERIDIID

Cecile Roux observed these small theridiids catching ants. She photographed their silk retreats hanging from the bottom of the Afrikaanse Taalmonument at Paarlberg close to the soil surface. There were about 15 of these retreats and most of them contained a spider feeding on a ant. The bell-shaped retreats are made of small pebbles and are open at the bottom and hang from single threads about 1-2 cm from the ground.

To build the retreat, the spider drops down to the soil surface, chooses a sand grain and attaches it to her hind legs. She then climbs back and attaches it to the retreat.

These nests resemble that of *Achaearanea globispira* from the Cedarberg but these ones hang free.

They are very small spiders.

Achaearanea sp. in their small hanging stone nests.. Photo credits: Cecile Roux

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

AZEVEDO, G.H.F., BOUGIE, T., CARBONI, M., HEDIN, M. & RAMÍREZ, M.J. 2022. Combining genomic, phenotypic and sanger sequencing data to elucidate the phylogeny of the two-clawed spiders (Dionycha). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 166(107327): 1-14.

BOOYSEN, R. & HADDAD, C.R. 2021. Season determines the efficiency of a rapid sampling protocol for non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) in Afrotropical grassland biotopes. *Austral Entomology* 60(4):19-21
<https://doi.org/10.1111/aen.12573>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., VAN ZYL, J. & WEBB, P. 2021. First record of *Eriovixia excelsa* (Simon, 1889) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 39: 21-23.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., LOTZ, L.N. & BIRD, T. 2021. A review of the spider species *Cheiracanthium furculatum* (Araneae: Cheiracanthiidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 39: 8-13.

EICHHOFF, A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & LUYT, J. 2021. Notes on the crevice-weaving spider *Andoharano ansieae* Zonstein & Marusik, 2015 in Southern Africa (Araneae: Filistatidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 39: 24-25.

HADDAD C.R. 2021. Undergraduate entomology field excursions are a valuable source of biodiversity data: A case for spider (Araneae) bycatches in ecological studies. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 30: 4199-4222.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-021-02301-9>

HADDAD C.R. 2021. Rediscovery and redescription of *Rhene cooperi* Lessert, 1925 (Araneae: Salticidae), another possible mimic of scale insects. *Arthropoda Selecta* 30(4): 546-550.

HADDAD, C.R. & FOORD, S.H. 2021. Future climate may limit the spread of the Australian house spider *Badumna longinqua* (Araneae: Desidae) in South Africa. *Journal of Arachnology* 49 (3), 332–339. <https://doi.org/10.1636/JoA-S-20-069>

JONES, A. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2021. Notes on the orb-web spiders of Mpetsane Conservancy Estate in the Free State (Arachnida: Araneae) - part 2. *SANSA Newsletter* 39: 14-18.

WIESE, L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2021. Notes on the rare nursery-web spider *Walrencea globosa* Blandin, 1979 in South Africa (Araneae: Pisauridae). *SANSA Newsletter* 39: 19-20.

ZONSTEIN, S. & MARUSIK, Y.M. 2021. The first Western Palearctic record of *Euprosthenoops* Pocock (Araneae, Pisauridae), with description of a new species from Israel. *ZooKeys* 1065: 13-27. doi:10.3897/zookeys.1065.74119

FEEDBACK ON EGGS OF A NEPHILA SPECIES

Tharina Bird sent us photographs of a *Nephila* egg sac that she photographed at the airport in Namibia in November 2008. She reported that she has frequently seen egg sacs hidden in vegetation near the *Nephila*'s webs.

SOME SANSA RESULTS FROM 2021

- New species described: Salticidae (5); Zodariidae (1); Tetragnathidae (4); Thomisidae (3); Gnaphosidae (11); Trachelidae (4); and Entypesidae (6) = 34.
- Identification guides produced: 33.
- Scientific publications: 20.
- Species newly listed on the WSC: 34.

New locality records for the white spotted crab spider *Firmicus bragantinus* (Brito Capello, 1866) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Vida van der Walt² & Peter Webb²

¹Department of Zoology, University of Venda. dippenaaransie@gmail.com ²SANSA team members, Gauteng, vidavdw2@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

The white spotted crab spider *Firmicus bragantinus* (Brito Capello, 1866) has been recorded throughout South Africa, extending its current distribution range in Africa from West Africa, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Angola, Sudan to South Africa. The general morphology of the species is described and photographs of live specimens are provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Firmicus* was described by Simon, 1895 with *Firmicus bragantinus* (Brito Capello, 1866) as the type species. The genus is represented by 19 species and subspecies, of which 16 are known from Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2021).

Firmicus bragantinus is an African endemic species described by Brito Capello, 1866 as *Thomisus bragantinus*. The species was then transferred by Lessert (1919) to *Synaema bragantinum* and again by Roewer (1955) to *F. bragantinus*.

The general morphology of the species is provided based on live specimens. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation status are provided.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). The voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division. Requests were also made for photographs of species for the SANSA Virtual Museum and sets of photographs of *F. bragantinus* have been received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Firmicus bragantinus (Brito Capello, 1866)

Thomisus bragantinus Brito Capello, 1866: 86

Synaema bragantinum Lessert, 1919: 195; Lessert, 1928: 320;

Lessert, 1933: 121, f. 37; Lessert, 1936: 260, f. 54-55

Firmicus bragantinus Roewer, 1955: 833.

Diagnostic characteristics: *Firmicus bragantinus* can be recognised by its slightly flattened body. The female is white, with distinct dark patterns on the body and legs (Fig. 1). Carapace is pale cream; anterior eye row is straight, with eyes equidistantly spaced; posterior eye row is recurved; anterior lateral eyes are slightly larger than others (Fig. 2); chelicerae has black spots. Abdomen is white, with black spots and transverse lines. Legs are white, with black spots, and black bands at legs joints; two front pairs longer than posterior pairs. Male is smaller in size, carapace orange-brown; abdomen with brown scutum with two pairs of black spots; front legs with femora and trochanters dark, rest of legs paler. Size: Total length: female and male 4-5 mm.

Figures 1-3. *Firmicus bragantinus*. 1. Female dorsal view. 2. Female anterior view. 3. Male dorsal view. Photo credits : 1-2. V van der Walt 3. Robin Lyle.

Figures 4-5. *Firmicus bragantinus*. 4. Female epigyne ventral view. 5. Male palp ventral view. Photo credits; Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Angola, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, South Africa and Sudan.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

KwaZulu-Natal: Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); iSimangaliso, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); Hluhluwe Hippo Pools (-28.02, 32.28). **Limpopo:** Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Kapama Private Game Reserve (-24.43, 31.03); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 0.25). **Mpumalanga:** Burgers Hall (-32.02, 31.08); Mbombela (-25.47, 30.96); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Ngwenya Lodge (-25.38, 31.85). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve.

Figure 6. South African records of *Firmicus bragantinus*.

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living plant-dwelling spiders that are more commonly found on shrubs and herbs. They are well camouflaged and blend in with the vegetation. They are usually sampled with sweeping and beating of the vegetation. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savannah biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Firmicus bragantinus is mainly active during the day, moving around on vegetation (Figs 7 & 8). The adults are abundant in the summer months, while the juveniles overwinter low in plant bases. They prey on a variety of small invertebrates that come within grasping distance. They have been sampled from avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), citrus and grapefruit orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 7. *Firmicus bragantinus* female sampled from Kapama in Limpopo. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

Figure 8. *Firmicus bragantinus* female sampled from Ngwenya Lodge in Mpumalanga. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION

In South Africa, the species is recorded from four provinces and it is found in seven protected areas: Kruger National Park, Sodwana Bay National Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve, Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009). No conservation actions are recommended. Due to its wide range and no known threats, it is listed as Least Concern.

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New information on the crowned crab spider *Parasmodix quadrituberculata* Jézéquel, 1966 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Ruan Booysen² & Rudi Steenkamp³

¹ Department of Zoology, University of Venda. dippenaaransie@gmail.com. ² Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State. booyesenr@ufs.ac.za. ³ The Spider Club of Southern Africa. rudolphsteinkampf@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

The crowned crab spider *Parasmodix quadrituberculata* Jézéquel, 1966 has been recorded from South Africa, extending its current distribution range in Africa from the Ivory Coast to South Africa. Very little is known about the species and although widely distributed in South Africa, they are not very commonly found. The general morphology of the species is described and photographs of live specimens provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Parasmodix* is monotypic and presently only known from *P. quadrituberculata* from the Ivory Coast (World Spider Catalog, 2022). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys are undertaken to document the South African spider fauna. Some of the material sampled were identified as *P. quadrituberculata*.

Except for the original description nothing is known about the species. In this paper we provide some information on their morphology based on photographs of live specimens, behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

SANSA surveys were undertaken throughout the country and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

TAXONOMY

Parasmodix quadrituberculata Jézéquel, 1966

Parasmodix quadrituberculatus Jézéquel, 1966: 628, f. 19-22

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female 4-5 mm. Carapace as wide as long (Fig. 1); chestnut brown with white band around carapace border (Fig. 2); with scattered short setae and a few longer setae present on truncated posterior edge of carapace, on clypeal edge and between lateral eyes and behind posterior lateral eyes; cephalic region high and slightly convex, sloping anteriorly; thoracic region truncated posteriorly (Fig. 2); eyes in two rows covering most of carapace width; both eye rows recurved (Fig. 7); anterior eye row slightly narrower than posterior eye row (Fig. 3); lateral eyes large with anterior median eyes smallest (Fig. 3); chelicerae with dorsal surface slightly flattened (Fig. 6); cheliceral ridge with upper edge rounded and slightly protruding with 7-9 inwardly curved spiniform setae. Abdomen oval; mottled with white and dark markings; lateral sides with white bands. Legs are pale yellow; femora and patellae of legs I and II dark brown; other legs with brown spots and lines (Fig. 8).

Figures 1-3. *Parasmodix quadrituberculata* female from Enseleni Nature Reserve 1. Female dorsal view 2. Female lateral view 3. Female anterior view. Photo credits : Ruan Booysen.

Figures 4-8. *Parasmoxid quadrituberculata*. 4. Female epigyne ventral view. 5. Female habitus. 6-7. Female eye pattern dorsal view. 8. Female anterior view. Photo credits : 4. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman 5-6. Robin Lyle 7-8. Ronel White.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Ivory Coast and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Gauteng: Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest (-28.31, 32.37); Isandlwana Nature Reserve (-28.36, 30.64); Mkhomazi State Forest (-29.62, 29.75); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.03, 32.42); Enseleni Nature Reserve (-28.68, 32.05). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.70); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Tuinplaas (-24.90, 28.73). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **North West:** Skeerpoort (-25.81, 27.75). **Western Cape:** Du Toits Kloof (-33.70, 19.27); 40 km NE Ceres, Touwsriver road (-33.36, 19.31).

Figure 9. South African records of *Parasmoxid quadrituberculata*.

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living plant-dwelling spiders that are more commonly found on shrubs, herbs and trees. They are well camouflaged and blend in with the vegetation. Very little is known about their behaviour and although widely distributed, they are not very commonly found.

They are usually sampled with sweeping and beating of the vegetation from the Grassland, Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savannah biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; 2013). Also sampled from maize fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). Adults were sampled throughout the year, and juveniles were sampled from May until October.

CONSERVATION STATUS

There are no significant threats to the species. Recorded from eight reserves such as Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2009), Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

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Notes on the silver vlei spider *Leucauge festiva* (Blackwall, 1866) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, A. Jones² & C.R. Haddad³

¹ Department of Zoology, University of Venda, South Africa, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ² SANSA team member, Spitskop Farm, Clocolan, South Africa, allenjones@lantic.net; ³ Department of Zoology & Entomology, University of the Free State, Bloemfontein 9300, South Africa, haddadcr@ufs.ac.za

Abstract: *Leucauge festiva* (Blackwall, 1866) is an African endemic described from Equatorial Africa. Little is known about their behaviour and notes are provided on their general morphology and distribution in South Africa with photographs on their webs and lifestyle.

Key words: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), Free State, web building.

INTRODUCTION

Leucauge White, 1841 is represented by 167 species with eight species known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). The species *Leucauge festiva* (Blackwall, 1866) is an African endemic described from equatorial Africa as *Tetragnatha festiva* (World Spider Catalog, 2021). They are brightly coloured and make orb webs in low vegetation. The aim of this paper is to add notes on the morphology of *L. festiva* based on images of living spiders, their behaviour and distribution.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), requests were made for photographs of species for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012). Most of the observations were made by the second author (AJ) in grassland at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) that is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands some 14 km from Clocolan. The MCE (28°48'S; 27°39'E) covers 164 ha and it is a registered conservancy (Amohela-ho-Spitskop) sanctuary and nature reserve. Several sets of photographs of *Leucauge* spp. have been received from the public. In several instances, the specimens were also sampled and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division.

TAXONOMY

Leucauge festiva (Blackwall, 1866)

Tetragnatha festiva Blackwall, 1866: 467.

Meta splendida Butler, 1883: 765, pl. 57, f. 3.

Leucauge festiva Tullgren, 1910: 153, pl. 3, f. 76; Wiehle, 1967: 193, f. 41.

Diagnostic characteristics: The species is recognised by the double fringe of trichobothria on the prolateral surface of the basal half of the posterior femora – a character present in all *Leucauge* species (Fig. 3). Size: TL 8–9 mm (males little smaller than females. Carapace is shiny yellow-brown; rounded in front and on the sides, slightly convex, with a large indentation in the medial line of the posterior region (Fig. 1); eyes on black spots on the anterior part of the cephalothorax; four median eyes nearly form a square; chelicerae short and thick and with strong projecting spurs, which are greatly enlarged in males (Fig. 9). Abdomen silvery, decorated with reddish mask with tints of maroon, yellow, gold and green, with distinct black spots on anterior and posterior end (Figs 4–5); abdomen elongate, sub-cylindrical with short posterior tip; ventrally with broad medial band varies from green to brown; bordered by thin white to yellow bands (Fig. 6). Legs are yellowish brown; long and slender with three claws, with many spines, posterior femora with double fringe of trichobothria. Male and female genitalia relatively simple; male embolus enclosed or coiled together with conductor (Fig. 8); female epigyne with fingerlike scape (Fig. 7).

Figures 1-5. *Leucauge festiva*. 1. Female dorsal view; 2. Male lateral view; 3. Leg 4 femur with trichobothria; 4. Abdomen of female; 5. Abdomen of male. Photo credits : 1-2 Peter Webb 3. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman 4-5. Allen Jones

Figures 6-9. *Leucauge festiva*: 6. Female abdomen ventral view; 7. Female epigyne dorsal view (C. Haddad); 8. Male palp (C. Haddad); 9. Male chelicerae ventral view (Ansie Dippenaar-Sxchoeman).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Eswatini (NCA), Ethiopia (Blackwall, 1866), Equatorial Africa (Blackwall, 1866), Namibia (Griffin & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991), South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), Tanzania (Tullgren, 1910), Kenya (Kioko *et al.*, 2021), Madagascar (Butler, 1883).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

As part of the SANSa, large numbers of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). They have been sampled from all provinces but there is only one record from the Northern Cape. They are abundant in the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2014) and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) but absent from more arid regions. The species was also sampled from avocado and macadamia orchards, as well as pumpkin and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). The species is protected in >10 reserves (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Due to the species' wide range, its International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) status is Least Concern.

COMMON NAMES

Species known as the masked silver vlei spider; red, gold and silver vlei spider and silver vlei spider.

BEHAVIOUR

Web construction: A common species at MCE that makes large symmetrical orb webs about 500-600 mm in diameter. They are almost always placed between long grass stalks, rarely between plant stalks, about 300-400 mm above the ground, so ideally positioned to catch grasshoppers – their usual prey. The inclination of the webs varies from vertical (Fig. 11) to horizontal (Fig. 12), and is often at an angle to the substrate (Fig. 13). The webs are left standing for days until the spider moves off to begin again at a new site. Old webs are abandoned and disintegrate naturally.

At MCE they do not necessarily live near water and are found in mountain grassland at 1 750-1 850 m above sea level. They often get frosted and misted at night. They only really appear in late sum-

Figures 10-14. *Leucauge festiva*: 10. Female on open hub of web; 11. Female in complete vertical web at night; 12. Female in web made in grass with horizontal inclination; 13. Female in web with slight inclination; 14. Female in open hub early in the morning. Photo credits: 10-14 Allen Jones.

Figures 15-17. *Leucauge festiva*: Close-ups of webs to show the variation in web structure. Photo credit: A. Jones.

The webs are large with an open hub in the middle. There is an open area between the hub and the sticky spirals that contains only radii. A typical *L. festiva* web contains 33-37 radii and the capture viscid part contains 35-38 spirals. When the web is horizontal the spider is found on the underside of the hub (Fig. 18). Sometimes two to three spiders share a web and do not seem to compete for space.

Figure 18 *Leucauge festiva* on horizontal web. Photo credit: J. van Zyl.

Figure 19. *Leucauge festiva* mating. Photo: H. de Klerk.

Mating and egg sacs: The male is smaller than the female and takes up a position parallel with her body during mating. Levi (1980) described an egg sac of *L. venusta* from Virginia constructed of fluffy orange-white silk, measuring approximately 8-9 mm in diameter, and containing several hundred eggs. The eggs were reddish-orange and approximately 0.4 mm in diameter. The egg sac is commonly attached to a leaf or twig near the edge of the web, and the shed exuviae often remain in the web for a period of time.

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More on the garden orb-web spider *Argiope australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Allen Jones²

¹ Department of Zoology, University of Venda, South Africa, AnsieDippenaar@gmail.com; ² SANSA team member, Spitskop Farm, Clocolan, South Africa, allenjones@lantic.net

Abstract: This paper provides information on the garden orb-web spider *Argiope australis* as observed in the Free State, South Africa. A large number of the specimens have been photographed. Information on their somatic variation, behaviour and distribution is provided.

Key words: South African National Survey of Arachnida, Free State, predation.

INTRODUCTION

Members of the genus *Argiope* Audouin, 1826 with their large size and bright colouration were some of the first tropical spiders to be described (*Araneoides capensis* Petiver, 1702).

Several species with lobed abdomens of the genus *Argiope* are known from the Afrotropical Region. However, there seems to be large variability in morphological features of these species, as well as their genitalia (Levi, 1983; Bjørn, 1997; Jäger, 2020). Due to this variation, Kolosvary (1938) argues that all lobed *Argiope* in Africa should be considered subspecies of *A. lobata* (Pallas, 1772), the type species of the genus. This variability makes species identification problematic, as can be seen in the >80 *Argiope* synonyms presently listed in the World Spider Catalog (2022).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), surveys were undertaken over a wide area and numerous *Argiope* specimens were collected, as well as photographs taken. Observations on several species were made during a 14-year survey in a grassland fragment at Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) in the Free State province, South Africa. *Argiope* species were some of the spiders closely monitored. Two species of lobed *Argiope* have been reported from the MCE: *A. australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) and *A. lobata* (Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2021). However, on closer inspection of the genitalia, we found that there are only two species of lobed *Argiope* in the MCE, namely *A. australis*, but large variations in body shape and colour were found.

In this paper, we provide information on *A. australis* observed in the field over a period of several years. A large number of the specimens have been observed and photographed. Information on their somatic variation is provided, as well as information on their behaviour and distribution.

METHOD

The survey was carried out in grassland at the MCE, which is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands some 14 km from Clocolan. The MCE (28°48'S; 27°39'E) covers 164 ha and is a registered conservancy (Amohela-ho-Spitskop) sanctuary and nature reserve. The estate is on average 1 700 m above sea level, with an annual rainfall of 720 mm. More than 1 000 photographs were taken of *Argiope* specimens and their webs at MCE. The photographs and observations were made by the second author (AJ). While staying on the reserve, he was able to regularly walk in the field to photograph spiders and make observations.

Figure 1. *Argiope australis* female in web at MCE. Photo credit Allen Jones

TAXONOMY

Argiope australis is an African endemic species described as *Epeira australis* from the Cape of Good Hope, South Africa and Ile de France (Mauritius), but no type material remains in existence. In order to obtain nomenclatural and taxonomical stability, Bjørn (1997) designated a female neotype herein from Zaire: Katanga, Kasapa (11°35'S 27°25'E).

In the revision of the African *Argiope* species, Bjørn (1997) examined all available material from 13 museums. This included 80 lobed *Argiope* specimens from the National Collection of Arachnida, South Africa. He recognised two species from South Africa: *A. lobata* and *A. australis*; however, the majority of specimens (76) belong to *A. australis* and only three were identified as *A. lobata* (Bjørn, 1997).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Argiope australis is recorded throughout the eastern part of Africa, from Sudan through South Africa, in the eastern part of Zaïre, as well as from Senegal and Angola.

Diagnostic characteristics: TL female 24-30 mm, male 5-7 mm. **Female:** Carapace with reflecting hairs; ocular area dark; thorax with sides more parallel; sternum with median pale patch (Fig. 1). Abdomen without shoulders, with bluntly rounded lateral lobes; sometimes with posterior tail; dorsal pattern consisting of 3-5 transverse bands that are variable (Fig. 2); ventrally with median dark band bordered by series of yellow spots (Fig. 4b); in juveniles bands sometimes yellow and more orange-red. Legs banded. Epigyne: Shape of epigynal roof is highly variable (Figs 3c-d), but roof always somewhat narrowed.

Variation: The colour of the abdomen varies from pale yellow, almost creamy (Fig. 2h), to a bright yellow (Fig. 2b); the transverse bands vary from dark and uninterrupted (Figs 2c-d, 2g) to faint (Figs 2a-b); interrupted (Fig. 2e); black to red (Fig. 2f) or black with reddish tint (Figs 2h-i).

Male: Carapace light brown with longitudinal darker brown band on each side of the fovea; ocular region with dark rings around eyes; thorax with almost parallel sides (Figs 4a-b). Coxae and trochanters light brown, legs light brown with darker spots. Abdominal dorsal pattern consisting of two longitudinal brown lines on white background; ventral pattern consisting of two paraxial white lines bordering greyish median area. Palp: The shape of the embolus thorn can vary to a large extent, ranging from merely acute through broad and spade like. The length of the thorn, however, is always longer (Figs 4c-d) than the width of the embolus just distal to the insertion of the thorn.

Figure 2. Abdomens of *Argiope australis* females taken at MCE showing the variation. Photo credit Allen Jones.

Figure 4. *Argiope australis*: a-b. Female's ventral view with male dorsal view; . Photo credit Rudi Steenkamp

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

The species is very commonly found in South Africa (Fig. 5). It was sampled from all the floral biomes in South Africa such as the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011). It was also collected from crops such as avocado, peach and pistachio orchards, pine plantations and pumpkin fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). In the past, they were frequently found in gardens – hence the common name.

Figure 3. *Argiope australis* females: a. Habitus after Bjørn (1997); b. Epigyne variation after Bjørn (1997); c-d. Epigyne variation. Photo credit Allen

Figure 5. *Argiope australis*: a. Female in web, ventral view with male; b. Male palp lateral view; c. Male palp after Bjørn (1997) Photo credit 5a Allen Jones

COMMON NAME

In South Africa, *A. australis* is known by several common names, such as butter spider, pumpkin spider, black and yellow banded spider or garden orb-web spiders.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

Argiope australis has been sampled from more than 30 protected areas, including national parks and reserves in all the provinces such as Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). No conservation actions are recommended. Due to its wide distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

BEHAVIOUR

Web: They typically spin a large orb-web 400-600 mm in diameter between strong grass stalks or even other plant stalks (Fig. 6). Generally built in open grassland, usually between tall stalks and low shrubs. The webs are dense with many radii, making it strong and it is well anchored. The webs are no more than 300-400 mm above ground. However, there is a record of a web built on top of a wild asparagus bush about 2 m high, a web that was used constantly for 62 days. They are present on the web day and night, even in frosty days and misty mornings. The spider hangs in the centre of the web, head facing downwards. They often use the same web for long periods, and periodical repairs are made when damage occurs (Fig. 7). The males were in their own webs and only a few were found in females' webs. The males are found around the margins of the web during the mating season, which is usually in summer (Fig. 5a).

Immature spiders (8-10 mm) make complete orb-webs, 200 mm above ground level. The web is a perfect miniature of the adult web and is about 180 mm in diameter. The adult females often make webs that are inclined to between 30-40 degrees or more from the vertical. This is clearly intended since the web does not sag. The strand tensions are perfectly designed to compensate for a spider with prey and to allow for wind effect, which will cause the whole web to ripple but not break.

Stabilimentum: They do not always make a stabilimentum in the web and webs have often been observed without one. The stabilimenta in webs are not very dense and can vary from a central strip stretching upwards or downwards (Figs 5a, 6-7).

Prey: The symmetrical orb-webs are clearly visible yet the spiders are extremely successful at catching a variety of prey such as butterflies, bees, flies, grasshoppers and even the occasional dragonfly. The prey is wrapped in silk through rapid movements of the hind legs, and is eaten when safely secured. After some rain at MCE, an "Argiope city" was discovered where 50-60 *Argiope* spider webs were present in the bushes. It was not common to find so many spiders present just in this one location on the farm, as they are normally found throughout the estate. The spiders were probably attracted to the high numbers of grasshoppers [Orthoptera Acrididae, *Truxalis* sp.] that were found in most webs (Fig. 8) (Jones, 2012).

Figure 6. *Argiope australis* female in new orb web. Photo credit Allen Jones

Figure 7. *Argiope australis* female in old orb web showing damage due to wind. Photo credit Allen Jones

Figure 8. *Argiope australis* female feeding on grasshoppers (Orthoptera Acrididae, *Truxalis* sp.) Photo credit Allen Jones

Predators: On several occasions dead spiders have been found killed by fiscal shrikes (*Lanius collaris*), also known as Jan Fiskaal, fiskaallaksman or “Jackie Hanger” (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. *Argiope australis* killed by fiscal shrikes (*Lanius collaris*). Photo credit Allen Jones

Spiders relocate frequently and they have a perfect sense for a new successful food source, and frequently congregate in numbers at an abundant site; clearly there is close communication among them. A female was photographed that had abandoned her web and embarked upon an epic journey, being such large heavy creatures they cannot balloon. She walked clambering over plants and grass leaves, occasionally stopping to rest. One female covered 3 m in 5 minutes of arduous effort. All the while she was exposed and totally vulnerable. She cannot feed along the way. New web sites are generally several hundred metres away. When she does arrive at a suitable site, she begins the process of creating a new web.

Figure 10. *Argiope australis* “walking” over grass to find a new web site. Photo credit Allen Jones

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SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Thyspunt, South Africa

Ansie S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Linda Wiese²

¹Department of Zoology, University of Venda, South Africa, dippenaaransie@gmail.com

²South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) Team, Eastern Cape, Jeffrey's Bay, South Africa, lwiese9@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), several surveys were undertaken in the Eastern Cape and this paper provides the first annotated species list of spiders presently known from Thyspunt, a small area in the Eastern Cape, marked for a possible nuclear installation. A total of 94 species from 75 genera and 26 families were recorded. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (19 spp.), Araneidae (19 spp.) and Thomisidae (15 spp.). The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species.

Keywords: South African National Survey of Arachnida, Western Cape, conservation assessment

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), 195 sites were sampled in the Eastern Cape but large areas have not been sampled yet. A total of 837 species, 38.6% of all South African species, have been recorded from the province (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2006; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). From the Eastern Cape, 23 protected areas have been sampled, mainly reserves, but also two national parks and state forest areas. In 13 of these areas, >50 specimens were sampled. The Mountain Zebra National Park was the first national park for which a species list was published (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988), with a subsequent update (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006). The second national park that was surveyed in the province was the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). Other published surveys include the Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011) and Silaka Nature Reserve (Forbanka & Niba, 2013). In the Asante Sana Nature Reserve in the Sneeuwberg Mountains, a long survey formed part of a PhD study (Midgley, 2012), looking at the structure of epigeic invertebrate communities along an altitudinal gradient. Staff and students of the University of the Free State have done extensive sampling in the Amatola Mountains in the Hogsback area, while the University of KwaZulu-Natal was involved in sampling in the Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011).

Other studies include behavioural studies on the subsocial eresid *Stegodyphus tentoriicola* Purcell, found in the Mountain Zebra National Park (Ruch *et al.*, 2009; 2012), while Wiese and Dippenaar-Schoeman (2021) reported on the pisaurid *Walrencea globosa* Blandin from Thyspunt.

This paper presents the first information on the spider fauna of Thyspunt, a small area in the Eastern Cape. Information on endemism and conservation status for 94 species is provided.

METHODS

Study area: Thyspunt (-34.1918°S; 24.7134°E) is a rocky stretch of coast just west of the Thysbaai beach. It is situated in a pristine 3 800-ha coastal site 5 km east of Oyster Bay and 12 km west of Cape St Francis and 17.3 km south of Humansdorp in the Eastern Cape (Fig. 1).

The site has an elevation of 12 m. The area is controversially earmarked by Eskom for the possible building of a 4 000-MW nuclear power station. It is defined by UNESCO as a "cultural landscape", as it has unique natural, historical and cultural qualities, and spiritual meaning for the local Khoe and San community. Rare fynbos is endemic to the area. Thyspunt has unique vegetation – St Francis Fynbos / Thicket Mosaic – which only occurs between Huisklip (near Oyster Bay) to the west and Cape Recife (Gqeberha) to the east, and nowhere else in the world. Over 60% has been transformed by urbanisation, agriculture, forestry and alien plant invasions and it is severely threatened. It falls within the Cape Floral Kingdom, which is recognised as a biodiversity hotspot of global importance and is also an endemic bird area. In the Thyspunt thickets, there are protected trees such as *Sideroxylon inerme* (white milkwood) and *Pittosporum viridiflorum* (cheesewood). There are several plants at Thyspunt that are of conservation concern and that are listed on the Red List of South African Plants.

Sampling methods and identification: Sampling was done by the second author (LW) on the following dates: 19, 26, and 28 October 2011; 17 December 2011; 9 February 2012; 21 March 2012 and 4 April 2012. She used the following collecting methods: active search, beating, leaf litter, and sweeping.

Specimens were photographed and preserved in 70% ethanol. Identifications were done in Pretoria by the first author (AS). Some of the specimens could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved.

Voucher specimens: Specimens were deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria.

Endemism value and conservation status: Detailed explanation of the indices to assess the endemism value and conservation status of each species can be found at the end of Appendix 1. It distinguishes between species only known from the type locality (6), the Eastern Cape (5), two adjoining provinces (4), South Africa (3), Southern Africa (2), Afrotropical Region (1), and finally areas outside the Afrotropical Region (0). The conservation status was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa.

Figures 1-4. Thyspunt: 1. Showing the vegetation types in Thyspunt; 2. *Pelargonium suburbanum* subsp. *suburbanum*; 3. *Agathosma stenopetala*; 4. *Capeochloa cincta* subsp. *sericea*. Photo credit Linda Wieses 2-4 Caryl Logie.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 94 species in 75 genera and 26 families were recorded (see Table 1; Appendix 1). Ten could not be identified to species level as they are probably new or still immature. Unfortunately, some of them belong to large families that require comprehensive revision to determine the taxonomic status and identity of these taxa.

Family diversity: Of the 26 spider families collected from Thyspunt (see Table 1; Appendix 1), the Salticidae (19 spp.), Araneidae (19 spp.) and Thomisidae (15 spp.) are the most species-rich families. In the Mkambathi Nature Reserve, the Theridiidae and Araneidae were the most species-rich families (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011), and at the Mountain Zebra National Park, it was the Thomisidae (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988; 2006), while at the Addo Elephant National Park, the Thomisidae (39 spp.), Araneidae (39 spp.), Salticidae (35 spp.) and Theridiidae (25 spp.) were the most species-rich families (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Species endemism: Of the 94 species sampled, only three species – *Neriene flammea* Van Helsdingen, 1969 (Linyphiidae), *Walrencea globosa* Blandin, 1979 (Pisauridae) and *Habrocestum laurae* Peckham and Peckham, 1903 (Pisauridae) – are data deficient (DD). Species of the families Araneidae (Fig. 7), Dictynidae (Fig. 11), Philodromidae (Fig. 16) and Theridiidae (Figs 26, 27) were not evaluated (NE) due to the taxonomic resolution of the respective genera. Seven of these species are possibly new to science.

Six species have a wide distribution and were possibly introduced to Africa. This includes several cosmopolitan species of the families Araneidae (*Cyclosa insulana*, *C. oculata*, *Cyrtophora citricola*, *Larinia chloris* and *Zygiella x-notata*) and two Theridiidae species (*Euryopsis funebris* and *Phycosoma martinae*).

Table 1: Spider diversity of Thyspunt with the total number of families, genera and species sampled

Family	Gen.	Spp.	Family	Gen.	Spp.
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Araneidae	16	19	Philodromidae	2	2
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	Pisauridae	3	3
Clubionidae	1	2	Salticidae	13	19
Corinnidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Cyatholipidae	1	1	Sparassidae	1	1
Dictynidae	1	1	Theridiidae	8	10
Eresidae	1	1	Thomisidae	9	15
Gnaphosidae	2	2	Trachelidae	2	2
Hahniidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Linyphiidae	2	2	Zodariidae	1	1
Mimetidae	1	1	Zoropsidae	1	1
Oxyopidae	2	3	Palpimanidae	1	1
			Total 26	75	94

Forty-one species are African endemics, 39 are Southern African endemics, and only eight are South African endemics and nine are near Eastern Cape endemics.

Table 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at Thyspunt (DD—Data deficient; NE—not evaluated; LC—Least Concern)

	No spp.	Code	%
Conservation status			
Data deficient (taxonomic reason or lack distribution data)	3	DD	3.1
Not evaluated (immature, new or undetermined)	8	NE	8.3
Least concern	83	LC	88.3
Vulnerable	0	VU	0
Endemism			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	6	LC	6.3
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	41	LC	43.6
2 – Southern Africa endemics (STHE)	15	LC	15.9
3 – South Africa endemics (SAE): more than three provinces	15	LC	15.9
4 – South Africa endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	9	LC/rare	9.6
5 – Eastern Cape endemics (ECE)	0	DD/rare	0
6 – Type locality	0	RARE	0

CONCLUSION

A total of 94 species were newly recorded from Thyspunt. All these data have been incorporated into the Spider Red Listing project. With the ecology and diversity of the spider fauna of South Africa so poorly known, each survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research.

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Figures 5-19. Spiders from Thyspunt: 5. *Neoscona rufipalpis* (Araneidae); 6. *Ideocaira transversa* (Araneidae); 7. *Acanthepeira* sp. (Araneidae); 8. *Gasteracantha sanguinolenta* (Araneidae); 9. *Gea infuscata* (Araneidae); 10. *Uzacisi capensis* (Cyatholipidae); 11. *Dictyna* sp. (Dictynidae); 12. *Aphantaulax signicollis* (Gnaphosidae); 13. *Hahnia laticeps* (Hahniidae); 14. *Hamataliwa fronticornis* (Oxyopidae); 15. *Palpimanus capensis* (Palpimanidae); 16. Philodromidae (new genus); 17. *Walrencea globosa* (Pisauridae); 18. *Chiasmopes lineatus* (Pisauridae); 19. *Euprosthonopsis pulchella* (Pisauridae). Photo credits: L. Wiese.

Figures 20-34. Spiders from Thyspunt: 20. *Brancus mustelus* (Salticidae); 21. *Myrmarachne laurentina* (Salticidae); 22. *Baryphas ahenus* (Salticidae); 23. *Leucauge thomeensis* (Tetragnathidae); 24. *Argyrodes zonatus* (Theridiidae); 25. *Theridion* sp. (Theridiidae); 26. *Phoroncidia* sp. (Theridiidae); 27. *Rubrorridion* sp. (Theridiidae); 28. *Euryopsis funebris* (Theridiidae); 29. *Pherecydes tuberculatus* (Thomisidae); 30. *Synema simoneae* (Thomisidae); 31. *Thomisops pupa* (male) (Thomisidae); 32. *Synema langheldi* (Thomisidae); 33. *Parabomis martini* (Thomisidae); 34. *Philoponella angolensis* (Uloboridae). Photo credits: L. Wiese.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Thyspunt, Eastern Cape, listing their endemcity (END), conservation status (CS) and global distribution (DIST), and known sex (F female, M male and B both) * possibly new species.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	SEX
AMAUROBIIDAE	<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE	F
ARANEIDAE	<i>Acanthepeira</i> sp.*		NE		
	<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	F
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Cyclosa oculata</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Gea infuscata</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Hypsosinga holzapfelae</i> (Lessert, 1936)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Ideocaira transversa</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE	F
	<i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Larinioides</i> sp.		NE		
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Zygiella x-notata</i> (Clerck, 1757)	0	LC		B
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	<i>Cheiramiona clavigera</i> (Simon, 1897)	3	LC	SAE	B
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC		B
	<i>Clubiona sigillata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE	M
CORINNIDAE	<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE	B
CYATHOLIPIDAE	<i>Ubacisi capensis</i> (Griswold, 1987)	4	LC	SAE	B
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.*		NE		
ERESIDAE	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE	B
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Aphantaulax signicollis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	F
	<i>Xerophaeus communis</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE	B
HAHNIIDAE	<i>Hahnia laticeps</i> Simon, 1898	3	LC	SAE	F
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Mecynidis dentipalpis</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE	M
	<i>Nerienne flammea</i> Van Helsdingen, 1969	4	DD	SAE	M
MIMETIDAE	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE	F
OXYOPIIDAE	<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE	F
	<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp.*		NE		
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	B
PHILODROMIDAE	New genus*		NE		
	<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE	B
PISAUROIDAE	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Euprosthénopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Walrencea globosa</i> Blandin, 1979	4	DD	SAE	B
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Brancus mustelus</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	M
	<i>Dendryphantes purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Habrocestum laurae</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4	DD	SAE	F
	<i>Harmochirus luculentus</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	SEX
	<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Myrmarachne laurentina</i> Bacelar, 1953	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Rhene lingularis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE	M
	<i>Rhene machadoi</i> Berland & Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Rhene timidus</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013	4	LC	SAE	F
	<i>Thyene leighi</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	M
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thyenula juvenca</i> Simon, 1902	3	LC	SAE	B
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	M
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE	B
TETRAGNATHIDAE	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Leucauge thomeensis</i> Kraus, 1960	1	LC	AE	M
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE	J
	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	1	LC	C	B
	<i>Phoroncidia</i> sp.*		NE		
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Rubroridion</i> sp.*		NE		
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Theridion</i> sp.*		NE		
THOMISIDAE	<i>Avelis hystriculus</i> Simon, 1895	3	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Oxytate leruthi</i> (Lessert, 1943)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Pherecydes nicolaasi</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	3	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1883	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Phrynarachne melloleitaoui</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Synema langheldi</i> Dahl, 1907	1	LC	AE	F
	<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	M
	<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	F
	<i>Thomisops pupa</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	1	LC	C	B
	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Afroseto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Thysanina transversa</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006	3	LC	SAE	B
ULOBORIDAE	<i>Miagrammopes longicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Philoponella angolensis</i> (Lessert, 1933)	1	LC	AE	M
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900	4	LC	SAE	J
ZOROPSIDAE	<i>Griswoldia urbensis</i> (Lawrence, 1942)	4	LC	SAE	B